

Barriers and Enabling Factors for Human Papilloma Virus Vaccination Among Saudi Parents

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Abstract

Introduction: Human Papillomavirus (HPV) is one of the most common sexually transmitted infections, with types 16 and 18 high risk causing the majority of cervical cancer cases. Despite the availability of effective vaccines, HPV vaccination rates remain low in Saudi Arabia. **Aim:** This study aims to assess the barriers and enabling factors influencing Saudi parents' decisions to vaccinate their daughters. **Methods:** A cross-sectional analytical study was conducted from September 2024 to April 2025, targeting Saudi parents with daughters aged 9 years or older. Data were collected via a questionnaire distributed through social media and primary healthcare centers. The questionnaire covered demographics, knowledge, enabling factors, barriers, and vaccination practices. **Results:** Chi square test revealed a significant association between higher knowledge and lower barriers ($p < 0.05$), while no significant relationship was observed between knowledge and enabling factors. Three enabling factors showed a significant positive association with vaccine uptake: belief that the vaccine has no side effects ($p = 0.02$), the view that prevention is better than treatment ($p = 0.04$), and healthcare provider recommendation ($p = 0.01$). All 17 identified barriers were significantly associated with lower vaccination rates. The most influential were the belief that the vaccine is unnecessary ($p = 0.0002$), previous negative vaccination experiences ($p = 0.0002$), and fear of side effects ($p = 0.001$). Overall, 60% of parents intended to delay vaccination, 22% refused it, and only 18% had vaccinated their daughters. Social media was the most reported source of information. **Conclusion:** Strengthening the role of trusted medical professionals and countering misinformation, especially in online spaces, is essential to improving vaccination coverage.

Keywords: *Human papillomavirus (HPV), Cervical cancer, Vaccination uptake, Enabling factors, Barriers.*

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Introduction

One of the most prevalent genital infections is the human papillomavirus (HPV) infection (Saudi Ministry of Health: Communicable Diseases, 2024; World Health Organization: Human papillomavirus and cancer, 2024; de Martel, et al., 2019). There are more than a hundred varieties of HPV. They are categorized into Low-risk HPV types, such as 6 and 11, are responsible for approximately 90% of benign conditions, including genital warts. In contrast, high-risk HPV types, notably 16 and 18, account for about 70% of cervical cancers. Other high-risk strains for HPV include 31, 33, 45, 52, and 58 which cause about 19% of cases of cervical cancer (Saudi Ministry of Health: Communicable Diseases, 2024).

Most people with HPV experience no significant symptoms or health problems, and in 90% of cases, the body clears the infection on its own within a few years. However, in some instances, a persistent HPV infection with high-risk HPV strains can lead to cervical cancer and also malignancies of the vulva, vagina, mouth/throat, and anus. It may take a woman with a healthy immune system 15 to 20 years to experience cervical alterations that result in cancer. In women with compromised immunity, changes could occur in five to ten years (Saudi Ministry of Health: Communicable Diseases, 2024; World Health Organization: Human papillomavirus and cancer, 2024; de Martel, et al., 2019).

HPV spreads through skin-to-skin contact, including sexual intercourse and any type of contact with the genital area, such as touching the genitalia of an infected person. It cannot spread by coming into contact with surfaces like toilet seats. Even when an individual with HPV shows no symptoms, the virus can still be

transmitted to others (Saudi Ministry of Health: Communicable Diseases, 2024). Currently, there is no treatment for HPV infection itself; however, there are treatments available its consequences of genital warts, cervical precancers, and cervical cancer (World Health Organization: Human papillomavirus and cancer, 2024).

Ninety percent of HPV infections can be prevented by the extremely efficient HPV vaccine (Saudi Ministry of Health: Communicable Diseases, 2024; de Martel, et al., 2019). The HPV vaccine consists of Virus-Like Particles (VLPs), which are inactivated particles that resemble the structure of the human papillomavirus but do not contain live viruses, making them safe for vaccination. Adjuvant substances are included to enhance the immune response, ensuring a more robust and effective vaccination outcome. The HPV vaccine is categorized based on the number of HPV strains they protect against, addressing both high-risk cancer-causing strains and those responsible for other conditions such as genital warts (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, n.d.). There is a bivalent vaccine targets HPV strains 16 and 18, which are responsible for about 70% of cervical cancer cases globally. These strains are considered the highest risk for causing malignancies in the cervix (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, n.d.). The quadrivalent vaccine provides coverage against four HPV strains: 6, 11, 16, and 18. While strains 16 and 18 are linked to cervical cancer, strains 6 and 11 cause genital warts. These vaccines offer broader protection against both cervical cancer and genital warts (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, n.d.).

The nonvalent vaccine, Gardasil 9, expands protection to cover nine HPV strains: 6, 11, 16,

18, 31, 33, 45, 52, and 58. This vaccine includes coverage for the same strains as the quadrivalent vaccine, with the addition of five more high-risk strains (31, 33, 45, 52, and 58), which account for an additional percentage of cervical cancer cases. Gardasil 9 provides the most comprehensive protection currently available (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, n.d.).

The HPV vaccine provides long-lasting immunity, with protection lasting at least 10 years. It is highly immunogenic, with over 98% of recipients generating a significant antibody response to the HPV types included in the vaccine just one month after completing the vaccination series. This robust response helps prevent persistent infections and reduces the risk of developing pre-cancerous conditions (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, n.d.).

Common side effects associated with HPV vaccination include injection site reactions of pain, swelling, and redness at the injection site, as well as systemic reactions of fever, nausea, and fatigue (Immunization, 2022). For young girls, the vaccination is offered as an elective immunization. It is usually advised that girls between the ages of 11 and 12 get the HPV vaccine to effectively prevent diseases caused by HPV. Additionally, vaccinations can begin as early as age 9. Women are typically more likely than men to be affected by the disease (Sait, et al., 2024).

Cervical cancer was the fourth leading cause of cancer and cancer-related deaths among women in 2022, with approximately 660,000 new cases and 350,000 deaths globally. Projections indicate that effective prevention could avert 300,000 deaths by 2030, over 14 million by 2070, and more than 62 million by 2120 (World Health Organization: Human papillomavirus and cancer, 2024). Cervical cancer ranks as the 8th most prevalent cancer among women in Saudi Arabia overall, as well as the 8th most common cancer among women aged 15 to 44 (ICO/IARC Information Centre on HPV and Cancer, 2023). According to a study published in *The Lancet Global Health*, cervical cancer remains a major concern, especially in low- and middle-income countries where the majority of cases and deaths occur. This creates a substantial

economic strain due to healthcare costs and loss of productivity (Singh, et al., 2022). In terms of economic cost, cervical cancer has placed a massive financial burden on the global economy, estimated to cost \$71.9 billion annually (Bencina, et al., 2024).

In response to this growing burden, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, the World Health Organization (WHO) launched the Global Strategy to Accelerate the Elimination of Cervical Cancer in November 2020. A key goal of the strategy is to achieve 90% HPV vaccination coverage among girls by age 15 by 2030, aiming to significantly reduce HPV-related diseases. To meet this target, efforts must focus on securing affordable vaccine supplies, expanding access to vaccination programs, and addressing social and cultural barriers to vaccine acceptance. Additionally, effective communication and community engagement are essential to overcome vaccine hesitancy. Implementing these strategies is expected to dramatically lower rates of HPV-related cancers, contributing to a healthier global population (World Health Organization, 2020).

The HPV burden findings emphasize the urgent need for scaling up preventive measures, especially in vulnerable groups, to alleviate both the health and economic impacts of cervical cancer and other adverse outcomes (Moshi, et al., 2024).

Previous studies showed that most Saudi women are unaware that HPV vaccinations are available (Moshi, et al., 2024). The majority of participants (74%) voiced doubts regarding the novel HPV vaccine's safety; vaccination uptake was low. This suggests that more research is necessary to determine the underlying reasons for this disparity (Al Saedi, Al Daajani, & Alghamdi, 2024).

About 70.6% of the parents of 296 participants in a different study carried out in Saudi Arabia were unaware of the HPV vaccine, and the majority of them were also unaware of the link between HPV and cervical cancer (Alshehri, Fahim, & Alsaigh, 2023). According to recent research, women do not receive enough information or recommendations for cervical cancer screening. Beyond awareness, there are

other obstacles to cervical cancer prevention, and vaccine hesitancy is one of the biggest ones. Unfortunately, few studies with limited sample sizes have been undertaken to investigate the level of cervical cancer awareness and women's acceptance of the HPV vaccine in various locations in Saudi Arabia (Moshi, et al., 2024).

Aim of the Study

To assess the barriers and enabling factors that affect Saudi parents' attitudes and practice towards HPV vaccination for their children.

Research Objectives

1. To identify the barriers that prevent Saudi parents from vaccinating their children against HPV.
2. To identify the main enabling factors that motivate Saudi parents to seek HPV vaccination for their children.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Population

This is a cross-sectional analytic study, targeting Saudi parents to assess the barriers and enabling factors for HPV vaccination. The study was conducted over a period of nearly eight months, starting on September 8, 2024, and concluding on April 30, 2025.

Sampling

A non-probability convenient sampling technique was employed to recruit the participants.

Sample size

The sample size was calculated using the formula:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{E^2} \quad (1)$$

Assuming a prevalence of 50% ($P = 0.5$), a 95% confidence level ($Z = 1.96$), and a 5% margin of error ($E = 0.05$), the calculation was as follows:

$$n = (1.96)^2 * 0.5 * (1 - 0.5) / (0.05)^2 \approx 384$$

Thus, a sample size of approximately 384 participants was required.

Data was collected through a pre-designed questionnaire developed using Google Forms. This questionnaire gathered socio-demographic details, knowledge, perceived barriers, enabling factors, and attitudes toward HPV vaccination. To maximize participation, the questionnaire link was distributed on social media platforms, including WhatsApp, Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), and Telegram. Additionally, printed QR codes were distributed in primary health care centers to ensure easy access for respondents.

The questionnaire section assesses HPV vaccine knowledge through one yes/no question and six multiple-choice questions, with a total score of 5. Scores of 0–3 indicate low knowledge (less than 75%), and 4–5 indicate high knowledge (more than 75%). The enabling factors for HPV vaccination were assessed using 14 questions rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree), with total score 70. Scores of 14–62 reflect low enabling factors (less than 75%), while >62–70 represent high enabling factors (more than 75%). The barriers to HPV vaccination were assessed using 17 questions on a Likert scale (5=strongly disagree to 1=strongly agree), with a total score of 85. Scores of 17–56 denote low barriers (less than 75%), and >56–85 indicate high barriers (more than 75%).

To validate the questionnaire, a forward-backward translation method was conducted to ensure that the final translation accurately reflected the intended meaning, addressed misunderstandings, ensured the questionnaire was clear, reliable, and relevant to the target audience, and reduced bias from poor translation. The questionnaire was then reviewed by three experts in the field, and based on their feedback, changes were made. Additionally, a pilot study on 30 parents was conducted to test the questionnaire's reliability. The Cronbach's alpha test was applied to the pilot study data, yielding an $\alpha = 0.9$ for both enabling factors and barriers, indicating excellent reliability of the questions, suggesting that the questions measured the same underlying construct.

Statistical analysis was done using JMP software (version 18 (New in JMP 18, n.d.). Barrier-related items were initially scored as follows: “Strongly agree” = 1, “Agree” = 2, “Neutral” = 3, “Disagree” = 4, and “Strongly disagree” = 5. These responses were then dichotomized: responses 1, 2, and 3 were coded as 0 (indicating no support for vaccination), while responses 4 and 5 were coded as 1 (indicating support for vaccination). For enabling factors, the original scoring ranged from “Strongly disagree” = 1 to “Strongly agree” = 5 and was recoded such that responses 1 and 2 were coded as 0 (no support for vaccination), and responses 3, 4, and 5 were coded as 1 (support for vaccination) (Alfaisal, et al., 2024). Chi-square tests were used to assess the association between knowledge and both barriers and enabling factors. Additionally, it was used for assessing the relationship between all barriers and enabling factors with HPV vaccine uptake. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Consideration

The data collection process began after obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB). Informed consent was obtained from each participant through an electronic consent form. Participants received a detailed explanation of the study's objectives and the purpose of collecting data. The voluntary nature of participation and the option to withdraw were explained to participants. Additionally, the confidentiality of the data obtained was preserved. Anonymity was ensured, the data were only utilized for research purposes, and there was no potential harm to the participants.

Funding

This research was self-funded by researchers. All necessary expenses, including data

Results

Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination practices among the study population. The findings reveal that the majority of parents (60%) reported they might postpone administering the vaccine, while only 18% of them said that their daughters had already received the vaccine at school or a medical center, while 22% of parents explicitly refused to vaccinate their daughters.

Figure 2 presents the sources of information about the human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine. The internet and social media appeared as the most common sources, reported by 37% of the participants. In comparison, mass media accounted for only 14% of the reported sources.

Figure 1. Proportion of Human Papilloma Virus Vaccination Practice among the Study Population

Figure 1. Sources of Information about the Human Papilloma Virus Vaccine

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population According to Vaccination Status

Variables	Vaccinated n=74	Not vaccinated n=335	P value
Parent:			
• Father	7 (9.5%)	17 (5.1%)	0.95
• Mother	67 (90.5%)	318 (94.9%)	
Age:			
• ≤34	8 (10.8%)	53 (15.8%)	0.1
• 35-45	40 (54.1%)	144 (43%)	
• 45+	26 (35.1%)	138 (41.2%)	
Education level			
• High school or less	21 (28.7%)	88 (26.3%)	0.7
• University degree or higher	53 (71.6%)	247 (73.7%)	
Employment status			
• Non-employed	30 (40.5%)	184 (54.9%)	0.06
• Non-healthcare worker	39 (52.7%)	139 (41.5%)	
• Healthcare worker	5 (6.8%)	12 (3.6%)	
Income level			
• < 10000	29 (39.2%)	160 (47.8%)	0.3
• 10000-20000	35 (47.3%)	143 (42.7%)	
• > 20000	10 (13.5%)	32 (9.6%)	
Marital status			
• Married	68 (91.9%)	300 (89.6%)	0.7
• Widow or divorced	6 (8.1%)	35 (10.5%)	

Table 1 represents the distribution of demographic characteristics among the study population (N=409). All demographic characteristics had no statistically significant

impact on vaccination status of the children. Most parents, whether they vaccinated their children (71.6%) or not (73.7%), had a university education or higher, and were married.

Table 2. Knowledge Score Categories by Enabling Factors and Barriers (N=409)

	High knowledge n=193	Low knowledge n=216	P value
Enabling factors:			
High enabling factors	58 (30.1%)	50 (23.1%)	0.11
Low enabling factors	135 (69.9%)	166 (76.9%)	
Barriers:			
High barriers	64 (33.2%)	39 (18.1%)	0.0004*
Low barriers	129 (66.8%)	177 (81.9%)	

Table 2 shows knowledge score categories by both enabling factors and barriers. More proportion of participants with low knowledge had low enabling factors (76.9 %) compared to those with high enabling factors (23.1%), but that was not statistically significant (p =0.11). In

contrast, more participants with high knowledge (66.8%) have shown low barriers as compared to those who have shown high barriers (33.2%). This relationship was statistically significant (p=0.0004).

Table 3. Association between Enabling Factors and HPV Vaccination Practice among Parents

ENABLING FACTORS	Vaccinated (n=74)	Not vaccinated (n=335)	P value
1. Have knowledge of cancer risk.	68 (91.9%)	302 (90.2%)	0.4
2. Vaccine has no side effects.	70 (94.6%)	288 (86%)	0.02*
3. Vaccine prevents cancer.	65 (87.9%)	292 (87.9%)	0.5
4. WHO and MOH recommendation.	72 (97.3%)	308 (92%)	0.07
5. Vaccine is Free of charge.	72 (97.3%)	309 (92.2%)	0.08
6. Nearby vaccination center.	70 (94.6%)	303 (90.5%)	0.1
7. Quick and easy vaccination process.	71 (96%)	309 (92.2%)	0.1
8. Personal experience with cancer.	63 (85.1%)	276 (82.4%)	0.3
9. Fear of cancer.	67 (90.6%)	278 (85.7%)	0.1
10. Prevention is better than treatment.	72 (97.3%)	305 (91%)	0.04*
11. Used in developed countries.	71 (96%)	300 (89.6%)	0.05
12. Friends have vaccinated their kids.	64 (86.5%)	272 (81.2%)	0.1
13. Health care providers recommendation.	70 (94.6%)	286 (85.4%)	0.01*
14. Attended Awareness campaigns.	68 (91.9%)	293 (87.5%)	0.1

Table 3 presents the association between various enabling factors and HPV vaccination practices among participating parents. Among the factors studied, only three showed a statistically significant association with vaccination uptake ($p < 0.05$): knowledge that the vaccine has no side effects, the belief that prevention is better

than treatment, and receiving a recommendation from healthcare providers. Although not statistically significant, it is noteworthy that 97.3% of parents who vaccinated their child reported that the vaccine was available free of charge.

Table 4. Association between Barriers Factors and HPV Vaccination Practice among Parents

BARRIERS	Vaccinated (N=74)	Not vaccinated (N=335)	P value
1. Vaccine is unnecessary	38 (51.4%)	96 (28.7%)	0.0002*
2. Lack of information	16 (21.6%)	42 (12.5%)	0.03*
3. Vaccine is unsafe	33 (44.6%)	87 (26%)	0.001*
4. Vaccine is ineffective	36 (48.7%)	106 (31.7%)	0.004*
5. Fear of side effects	22 (29.8%)	47 (14%)	0.001*
6. Past bad experience with vaccinations	42 (56.8%)	113 (33.8%)	0.0002*
7. Don't know where to go	40 (54.1%)	126 (37.6%)	0.007*
8. Center is too far	42 (56.8%)	138 (41.2%)	0.01*
9. Long procedures and wait	37 (50%)	104 (31%)	0.001*
10. Child is too young	24 (32.4%)	64 (19.1%)	0.01*
11. Multiple doses needed	29 (39.2%)	67 (20%)	0.0006*
12. Distrust in pharma companies	28 (37.8%)	70 (20.9%)	0.002*
13. No time	39 (52.7%)	124 (37%)	0.009*
14. Not mandatory.	28 (37.8%)	87 (26%)	0.02*
15. Forgot about it	36 (38.7%)	112 (33.4)	0.01*
16. Negative social media	31 (41.9%)	86 (25.7%)	0.004*
17. No support from family/friends	28 (37.8%)	89 (26.6%)	0.03*

Table 4 presents the association between various barriers and HPV vaccination practices among parents. The analysis shows that all the 17 investigated barriers were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), but three barriers occurred in higher proportion among the parents who did not vaccinate. These barriers are the center is too far, don't know where to vaccinate, and past bad experience with vaccinations.

Discussion

This study aims to assess the barriers and enabling factors affecting the Saudi parents' decision to vaccinate their children against human papilloma virus. Understanding the factors that influence parents' decisions to vaccinate their children against HPV is essential for improving public health strategies against HPV infection.

Alotaibi et al., (2024) in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, in their study titled "Maternal education and childhood immunization status in Saudi Arabia." found a significant correlation between higher maternal education levels and increased vaccination rates among children which reinforces the idea that higher academic education is closely linked to better health awareness and tend to have better access to, and understanding of, health-related information, which directly influences health decisions such as vaccination (Alotaibi, et al., 2024). In contrast to the findings of the current study, no significant association was found between parents' educational level and their decision to vaccinate their children against HPV (Table 1). This lack of significance may be attributed to the characteristics of our sample. Both vaccination groups included a high proportion of university-educated parents, which likely reduced the variability necessary to observe a statistical relationship. Furthermore, since the survey was distributed online, it is probable that participants were more digitally literate and, in many cases, more highly educated, resulting in a relatively homogeneous sample. Additionally, the use of a convenience sampling method may have further contributed to this homogeneity. Collectively, these factors may have constrained our ability to

detect a statistically significant impact of education on vaccination behavior.

In the present study, the association between enabling factors and knowledge, as shown in Table 2, was not statistically significant ($p = 0.11$). This is similar to a study conducted in Hail, Saudi Arabia, examined university students' knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions regarding Human Papillomavirus and its vaccine by Alshammari et al., (2022). The study found that knowledge about HPV was not significantly associated with similar enabling factors that were included in the current study that typically influence vaccination uptake. This suggests that simply increasing knowledge about HPV may not be sufficient to enhance vaccine acceptance. Other influencing factors such as cultural beliefs and all the barriers that were examined in the current study may play more pivotal roles. Therefore, public health strategies aiming to increase HPV vaccination rates should consider a multifaceted approach that goes beyond knowledge dissemination to address these other influential factors (Alshammari, & Khan, 2022).

The perceived barriers demonstrated a statistically significant association with knowledge ($p = 0.0004$) as shown in Table 2. A cross-sectional study conducted in the western region of Saudi Arabia examined the relationship between individuals' knowledge about HPV and its vaccine and their perceived barriers to vaccination Alshamrani et al., (2024), which found that participants with greater knowledge about HPV and its vaccine were significantly less likely to report barriers to vaccination. Specifically, multiple linear regression analysis revealed that increased knowledge was associated with a decrease in perceived barriers ($p < 0.001$), even after controlling demographic variables such as age, gender, marital status, employment, education, and income. This suggests that enhancing public knowledge about HPV and its vaccine could play a crucial role in reducing hesitancy and improving vaccination uptake (Alshamrani, et al., 2024).

In (table 3) among the 14 enabling factors examined using the chi-square test, only three showed a statistically significant association with

HPV vaccination uptake: the belief that the vaccine has no side effects ($p = 0.02$), the perception that prevention is better than treatment ($p = 0.04$) and receiving a recommendation from healthcare providers ($p = 0.01$). A recent national cross-sectional study conducted in Saudi Arabia by Faqeeh et al., (2024) named perceptions, Attitudes, and Barriers to Human Papillomavirus Vaccination Among Residents in Saudi Arabia examined factors influencing HPV vaccine uptake among residents. The study found that both the belief that the HPV vaccine has no side effects and receiving a recommendation from a healthcare provider were significantly associated with higher vaccination rates. These findings highlight the importance of addressing safety concerns and the influential role of healthcare providers in promoting vaccine uptake (Faqeeh, et al., 2024).

Table 3 of this study showed that the “concept of prevention being better than treatment” was a significant factor in HPV vaccine uptake, which is consistent with findings from Al-Mohaithef et al., (2020), who conducted a national web based survey among adults in Saudi Arabia titled “Determinants of COVID19 vaccine acceptance in Saudi Arabia” and found that individuals who saw vaccination as a preventive tool rather than waiting for treatment after infection were more likely to get vaccinated by focusing on prevention people are more likely to take action when they perceive the risk of an infection such as HPV to be high This supports the broader public health principle that emphasizes the effectiveness of preventive measures such as vaccination in reducing the long-term burden of diseases like HPV (Al-Mohaithef, & Padhi, 2020).

But interestingly, one of the enabling factors isn't statistically significant which is “vaccination is free of charge” contrary to a recent study Alrashidi et al., (2024) conducted in Saudi Arabia with title “Factors influencing human papillomavirus vaccine uptake among parents and teachers of schoolgirls “provides evidence that offering the HPV vaccine free of charge significantly influences its uptake (Alrashidi, et al., 2024).

In current study, despite the vaccine being free, social, cultural factors, and other barriers have stronger impact on the lower vaccine uptake, which was suggested by Al-Ghamdi et al. (2020), who identified similar barriers to HPV vaccine acceptance in Saudi Arabia and concluded that social and cultural factors played a significant role in limiting vaccine uptake, even when the vaccine was provided free of charge (Al-Ghamdi, et al., 2020).

All the investigated barriers in the current study are statically significant which means they had great impact on limiting vaccine uptake practice (Table 4). From the barriers are “concerns about center location being too far” and “don't know where to vaccinate” which are similar to Othman's et al., (2025) who conducted a study of prevalence of HPV vaccine hesitancy among adolescent females in Saudi Arabia and concluded that Key factors associated with this hesitancy included logistical challenges such as the distance to vaccination centers and uncertainty about where to obtain the vaccine (Othman, et al., 2025).

In this study “having a past bad experience with vaccination” was identified as a barrier to HPV vaccine uptake. This finding aligns with a nationwide study titled “Assessing Saudi women's awareness about human papillomavirus and their susceptibility to receive the vaccine” conducted by Alqarni et al., (2024), which reported that 15% of Saudi women hesitated to receive the HPV vaccine due to experiencing severe side effects following the COVID-19 vaccine. These results highlight the significant impact that negative previous vaccination experiences can have on the acceptance of other vaccines, emphasizing the need to address safety concerns and rebuild trust in vaccination programs (Alqarni, et al., 2024).

Figure 1 shows that 60% of parents reported “they may give the HPV vaccine later”, and 22% “refused the vaccine” resulting in more than 80% of the study parents did not decide to vaccinate their daughters which is much more higher than Othman's et a., (2025) who conducted a study in Saudi Arabia among parents of adolescent females and revealed HPV vaccine hesitancy is 34% of the 667 participants

(Othman, et al., 2025). This reflects a high level of vaccine hesitancy in this study, which may result from the mix of barriers and requires integrated approaches to motivate the parents to vaccinate their children. A recent study conducted in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia by Al Saedi, et al., (2024) identified several factors contributing to the spread of rumors and misconceptions about the Human Papilloma virus vaccine among parents, leading to vaccine hesitancy. The study highlighted that a significant proportion of parents held false beliefs regarding the target population for the vaccine and its effectiveness in preventing HPV-related cancers. Misinformation, primarily disseminated through the Internet and social media, was found to be a major contributor to these misconceptions, which were detected also in current study (Al Saedi, et al., 2024).

Despite growing efforts to promote HPV vaccination, several persistent myths continue to contribute to vaccine hesitancy among parents and adolescents. A common misconception is that the HPV vaccine is unsafe, particularly in communities with limited access to reliable health (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, n.d.).

Some individuals believe that the HPV vaccine does not offer sufficient protection because it does not cover all HPV strains. However, research titled “Human papillomavirus vaccination in Saudi Arabia” conducted by Alqahtani et al., (2025) has confirmed that the vaccine provides broad and effective protection against the most high-risk types of the virus.

Figure 2 indicates that the most common source of HPV vaccine information was the internet and social media (37%), followed by others (22%), family/friends (15%), mass media (14%), and healthcare providers (12%). The prominence of online platforms suggests a shift in how individuals seek health information, and that is supported by cross-sectional study conducted in Tabuk City assessed HPV vaccine awareness among 947 parents of intermediate schoolgirls by Safa et al., (2022). The study found that the primary sources of information were social media (26.6%), surpassing healthcare practitioners (12.7%). The reliance on the

internet and social media as primary information sources underscores the necessity for public health authorities to ensure accurate and accessible online content about HPV vaccination. Addressing misinformation and enhancing digital health literacy could play a pivotal role in improving vaccine uptake (Alaamri, et al., 2023).

Conclusion

This study underscores the complex interplay between enabling factors, perceived barriers, and parental decisions regarding HPV vaccination. While knowledge and accessibility are important, the strongest influences on vaccine uptake were belief in vaccine safety, trust in healthcare provider recommendations, and the perception that prevention is better than treatment. Conversely, concerns about vaccine necessity and prior negative experiences were major deterrents. Strengthening the role of trusted medical professionals and countering misinformation, especially in online spaces, is essential to improving HPV vaccination coverage.

Limitations

The use of a convenience sampling method may restrict the generalizability of the results, as it may not represent the broader population of Saudi parents. In addition, relying on self-reported responses introduces the possibility of recall bias or social desirability bias, particularly in reporting vaccine-related beliefs.

Strengths

This study addresses a significant and emerging health issue in Saudi Arabia. By focusing on Saudi parents with daughters aged 9 and above, it offers valuable insights to support local health programs in boosting HPV vaccination rates and preventing its serious consequences.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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